

1 Supplementary information

2 *Varying the fraction of substitutions on the nodes*

3 The fraction f_c is given by:

$$f_c = \frac{\tau(2N + H)}{\tau(2N + H) + \sum_i b_i} \quad (S1)$$

4 where N indicates the number of internal nodes of the tree, H indicates the
5 number of hidden nodes, b_i indicates the length of branch i and τ indicates the
6 time spent on the node.

7 Firstly, we verified correctness of equation S1 by keeping track of accumulated
8 branches during simulating alignments. We then a posteriori estimated the
9 observed fraction of substitutions accumulated at the nodes, for a sequence of
10 10000 bp, with a substitution rate of $1e-3$, for d in $[0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5]$, τ in $[0, 0.01,$
11 $0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4]$ times the crown age and using 100 replicates per parameter
12 combination. Results in figure S1 show that the expected fraction of substitution
13 on the nodes closely follows the observed fraction. Furthermore, the used values
14 of τ (which align with the values of τ used in the main text) explore a range of f_c
15 in $[0, 0.75]$, which seems reasonable.

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17 Figure S1. Top row: Observed fraction of substitutions accumulated at the nodes
 18 plotted against τ as a fraction of the crown age. Shown are results for different
 19 degrees of extinction varying in [0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5]. Per parameter combination, 100
 20 replicates were run. Bottom row: same parameter combinations but now
 21 showing the observed and expected f_c , following equation (3). The solid line
 22 indicates the observed = expected line.
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24 Secondly, we varied the fraction f_c of substitutions accumulated at the nodes
 25 compared to the total number of substitutions accumulated across the tree. We
 26 varied this fraction in [0.0, 0.1, 0.2, ..., 0.9]. Using equation (3) we computed a
 27 new value for τ , given a simulated tree. For each combination of extinction rate
 28 and f_c we simulated 100 true trees and generated one node substitution
 29 alignment and one *twin* alignment.

30 Figure S2 shows that results echo the results in the main text: with an increasing
 31 impact of node substitutions, summary statistics associated with branching
 32 times are affected most.

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35 Figure S2. Difference in summary statistic values between trees inferred from an
 36 alignment generated with node substitutions (colored boxplots), and *twin* trees
 37 that were inferred from an alignment generated without node substitutions
 38 (grey boxplots). Shown is the difference with the true tree. We explore different
 39 fractions of time spent on the nodes (τ , horizontal axis), and the impact of
 40 extinction (m , columns). The dotted line indicates zero difference between the
 41 two substitution models. Shown are results for the beta and gamma statistic, the
 42 Laplacian spectrum, the mean branch length, the nLTT statistic and crown age.
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44

45 Figure S3. Marginal likelihood weight of the relaxed and strict clock model, when
 46 tested on alignments generated with a node substitution model (top row) or
 47 without node substitutions (bottom row). Per fraction of time spent on the
 48 nodes, 100 replicate trees were analyzed. Because many of the replicates share
 49 the same weights and are plotted on top of each other, solid lines indicate the
 50 best fitting generalized additive model (gam), and the 95% Confidence interval
 51 (grey shaded area) of the gam. When the fraction of time spent on the nodes
 52 increases, posterior support for the relaxed clock model increases, but only if the
 53 alignment was generated with a node substitution model.

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56 *Linked model*

57 In addition to the model proposed in the main text, we studied a linked model,

58 where both daughter branches accumulate substitutions dependent on each

59 other, e.g. where accumulation of a substitution in one daughter branch excludes

60 the other daughter from accumulating the same substitution (at the node).

61 Similarly, this also precludes occurrence of a simultaneous mutation to the same

62 base in both daughter sequences. The linked node substitution model reflects

63 potential divergent sequence evolution, where evolution of a specific sequence in

64 one daughter drives evolution of a divergent sequence in the other daughter.

65 The linked substitution model is only applied at the node and not at the

66 subsequent branches. The transition matrix for the linked model is given by:

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68 $Q_1 =$

	AA	TT	CC	GG	AC	AT	AG	TC	TG	CG
A	*	0	0	0	1	1	1	α	α	α
T	0	*	0	0	α	1	α	1	1	α
C	0	0	*	0	1	α	α	1	α	1
G	0	0	0	*	α	α	1	α	1	1

69

70 where the letter on the left-hand side indicates the base present in the sequence

71 before the node and the two letters on top of the table indicate the letters

72 present in the two daughter sequences after the node. Thus, with rate one a

73 single mutation occurs, for instance from A to AT, where one daughter branch

74 inherits an A and the other daughter branch inherits a T. We do not keep track of
75 the identity of the daughter branches, and mutations are distributed randomly
76 over the two daughter branches. Similarly, with a rate of α , two mutations occur,
77 and both daughter branches inherit a base that is different from the parental
78 base, and that are different from each other. Lastly, we assume that daughter
79 branches cannot mutate to the same base. To apply the linked \mathbf{Q}_l matrix, we
80 extend it with zeros to make it a square matrix, and then calculate the transition
81 matrix \mathbf{P}_c , which now generates two sequences simultaneously.

82 Figure S3 shows results for the same analysis as performed for Figure 1 in the
83 main text, but now using the linked model. Because the linked model generates
84 fewer substitutions, effects are less strong, but as for to the unlinked model we
85 find that for statistics related to branching times, with increasing values of τ ,
86 the residual error increases.

87

88 Figure S4. Difference in summary statistic values between the true tree and trees
 89 inferred from an alignment generated with node substitutions using the *linked*
 90 model (colored boxplots), and *twin* trees that were inferred from an alignment
 91 generated without node substitutions (grey boxplots). Shown are results for
 92 trees inferred using a strict clock model, and a relaxed clock model. We explore τ
 93 as a fraction of crown age (horizontal axis), and the impact of extinction (d ,
 94 columns). The dotted line indicates zero difference with the true tree. The
 95 summary statistics are the beta and gamma statistic, Laplacian spectrum, mean
 96 branch length, nLTT statistic and crown age.
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98 Node density effect

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100 To assess the impact of the node density effect, we repeated the analysis from
101 Figure 1, but using an explicit simulation framework. For this we computed the
102 probability $P(n,i)$ of observing nucleotide i at time t where in total n substitutions
103 have taken place at this locus (including reverse mutations). Let us assume that
104 we start with $i = A$ at $t = 0$, so $P_0(0,A) = 1$ and $P_0(n > 0,A) = P_0(n \geq 0, \neg A) = 0$
105 (where \neg means not, i.e. $\neg A$ is either C, G or T). Then we can write the dynamics
106 for $P_t(0, A)$ and $P_t(0, \neg A)$ as, dropping the subscript t for notational simplicity:

$$107 \quad P'(0,A) = -3\mu P(0,A)$$

$$108 \quad P'(0,\neg A) = 0$$

109 where ' denotes the time derivative. The solution of these equations for the
110 abovementioned initial condition is $P(0, A) = \exp(-3\mu t)$ and $P(0, \neg A) = 0$.

111 The equations for $P(1, A)$ and $P(1, \neg A)$ are: $P'(1, A) = 3\mu P(0, \neg A) - 3\mu P(1, A)$

$$112 \quad P'(1, \neg A) = 2\mu P(0, \neg A) + \mu P(0, A) - 3\mu P(1, \neg A)$$

113 We can substitute the solutions for $P(0,A)$ and $P(0, \neg A)$ here and use the initial
114 condition to find that $P(1, A) = 0$ and $P(1, \neg A) = \mu t \exp(-3\mu t)$.

115 Similarly the equations for $P(2, A)$ and $P(2, \neg A)$ are:

$$116 \quad P'(2, A) = 3\mu P(1, \neg A) - 3\mu P(2, A)$$

$$117 \quad P'(2, \neg A) = 2\mu P(1, \neg A) + \mu P(1, A) - 3\mu P(2, \neg A)$$

118 for which the solution is: $P(2, A) = 3/2 \mu^2 t^2 \exp(-3\mu t)$ and $P(2, \neg A) = \mu^2 t^2 \exp(-$
119 $3\mu t)$.

120 We can continue in this way and find that the equations are given by

$$121 \quad P'(n, A) = 3\mu P(n - 1, \neg A) - 3\mu P(n, A)$$

$$122 \quad P'(n, \neg A) = 2\mu P(n - 1, \neg A) + \mu P(n - 1, A) - 3\mu P(n, \neg A)$$

123 and the general solution is:

124 $P(n, A) = a_n (\mu t)^n \exp(-3\mu t)$

125 $P(n, \neg A) = b_n (\mu t)^n \exp(-3\mu t)$

126 where

127 $a_n = 3b_{n-1} / n$

128 $b_n = (a_{n-1} + 2b_{n-1}) / n$

129 with $a_0 = 1$ and $b_0 = 0$.

130 We used these equations to generate sequences and then repeated the analysis

131 as performed for Figure 1 in the main text, now knowing the exact number of

132 substitutions that occurred. Figure S5 shows that results obtained are highly

133 similar to the patterns found in the main text, demonstrating that the results in

134 the main text correct adequately for the node-density-effect.

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136 Figure S5. Identical to Figure 1 in the main text, except that mutations were
137 simulated using the framework described above, both for sequences simulated
138 with node substitutions and sequences simulated using the model with
139 substitutions only on branches.